

D7.7

Sustainability protocol in olive oil production

Date: 14/01/2025

Version: 2.0

**Funded by
the European Union**

SOIL O-LIVE (Grant Agreement ID: 101091255) is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EIC. Neither the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Deliverable 7.7 Sustainability protocol in olive oil production

Document Information

Project title	SOIL BIODIVERSITY AND FUNCTIONALITY OF MEDITERRANEAN OLIVE GROVES
Project acronym	SOIL O-LIVE
Grant Agreement	101091255
Work package	WP1 - Coordination and management
Deliverable number and title	D7.7 Sustainability protocol in olive oil production
Deliverable description	Deoleo's sustainability protocol for the production of extra virgin olive oil
Deliverable type	R— Document, report
Dissemination level	PU
Lead beneficiary	DEOLEO
Due submission date	31/03/2023
Submission date	02.05.2025

Document Author(s) and Reviewer(s)

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Document history

Version	Date	Made by	Short Description of Changes
1.0	10/04/2023	Juan Carrasco Vilchez	First edition of the document
2.0	14/01/2025	Juan Carrasco Vilchez	Updated version after RP1

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Executive Summary

The European project SOIL O LIVE focuses on soil health in Mediterranean olive groves. In its first phase, more than 500 soil samples were analyzed from 52 farms in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Italy and Morocco.

Deoleo, as a member of the consortium, has developed a sustainability protocol that has been presented at various training sessions.

This protocol emphasizes the importance of sustainable practices to improve soil health and sustainable olive oil production.

The practices are applicable to olive groves and/or oil mills and cover various environmental, social, economic and quality aspects.

In total, it includes 235 actions at different levels and is intended to be a tool for the dissemination and implementation of sustainable practices.

Sustainability protocol in olive oil production

Deoleo®
The Olive Oil Company.

Sustainability Protocol

The Handbook

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Introduction

Launched in 2018, our Sustainability Protocol for Extra Virgin Olive Oil Production has already supported more than 40,000 farmers and 70 mills, guiding them to achieve high standards of sustainability through a holistic approach.

The Protocol is an invaluable resource for farms and mills who want to tackle the increasing quality, environmental, social and economic challenges that they currently face. By following the Protocol and working together with technicians from Deoleo, farms and mills can boost their operational resilience, help to safeguard rural livelihoods and support their economic development, both today and for generations to come.

Our Protocol acts as a handbook, designed to nurture and protect people, the planet and the legacy of olive oil. We are proud to share our values with those who we work with and create valuable partnerships which help to build a better future for our sector.

About Deoleo

For centuries, Deoleo's olive oil has been a household staple for kitchens around the globe. Our mission is to provide Mediterranean goodness through outstanding products, delivering premium quality to all who consume our products.

Armed with in-depth knowledge and passion, we produce high-quality olive oil blends and use our position in the sector to drive positive change.

Building on a legacy of proud craft, we now look to the future. We are empowering farmers to create businesses that promote thriving livelihoods while preserving the natural world. At the same time, we are innovating products which support healthier, more balanced lifestyles for our customers.

Creating value for all

Deoleo's brands delight consumers all over the world, known for their great taste and high quality. At Deoleo, quality is more than just a word – it is our main focus at each stage of the production process – starting in the soil of the olive groves, all the way to the materials we choose to bottle our product. We know that quality processes are those which are sustainable, and which create a positive impact for the future. From tree to table, we are committed to creating shared value for all stakeholders.

We acknowledge the role we play as global leaders in the sector, using this as a platform to promote the most sustainable and ethical practices, champion the need for quality control, and constantly finding ways to exceed customer expectations.

Deoleo is committed to creating value at each stage of the olive oil process – from supporting the farmers who grow the olives to communicating transparently with the consumers who enjoy our products. As a company rooted in heritage and legacy, we also look ahead, always looking for innovative ways to preserve this sector and generate value for many years to come.

Sustainability at Deoleo

We are committed to embedding sustainability into everything we do – within our own business and across our entire value chain – to continue nurturing a healthier future and make Mediterranean goodness available to all for years to come.

Olive oil is at the heart of so many lives – from those who grow the olives, to those who masterfully blend and bottle it, and the consumers who enjoy the benefits of good olive oil every day. As leaders in our sector, we know the potential we have to create positive change at each stage of the process. This is why we want to go beyond being the world's number one olive oil company to be the one with the greatest impact.

Our strategy to always care for what cares for you means that we bring our consumers olive oil that, as well as tasting great, has been produced responsibly and expertly. That's why we work across the value chain to promote improved livelihoods, good health and protection of our planet.

Internally, we focus our sustainability strategy and 2030 goals on three pillars – committing to conduct business responsibly at every stage of production and working with the relevant stakeholders to achieve the goals.

Our Sustainability Protocol is the tool that supports us in advancing our legacy of sustainability through our supply chain – to nurture and protect people, the planet and the heritage of olive oil.

14,293 farming hectares
visited by Deoleo technicians in 2021

192.5 million litres of olive oil
sold in 73 countries in 2021

Our business model relies on:

Natural resources including energy and water, and our key raw material, olives. We sourced olive oil from more than 300 suppliers in 2021.

Two factories with machinery dedicated to processing and packaging products.

A global workforce of 660+ employees.

Capital invested in long-term, sustainable growth – contributing to a 6% increase in sales in 2021.

Strong relationships with farmers, mills and retail customers. In 2021, we worked with 390 olive oil suppliers, co-packers and packaging suppliers.

Intellectual property of our unique blends.

Deoleo's 2030 sustainability strategy

Growing together

We care for the land and the farmers who depend on it.

- Building a responsible supply chain working with farmers to develop more sustainable practices, enable traceability and nurture responsible businesses
- Supporting farmer livelihoods by supporting global commitments to sustainable agriculture, helping rural communities prosper and promoting gender equity

Blending with love

We relentlessly pursue the highest possible standards in our operations.

- Delivering products with integrity by standardising extra virgin olive oil processes
- Designing out waste and reducing our environmental impact by optimising processes and operations, using materials more efficiently and diverting waste from landfill for repurposing

Caring for you

We promote wellbeing for our consumers and employees.

- Enabling nutrition and good adult health through customer education, sharing nutritional information and investing in scientific research into olive oil
- Respecting and supporting a diverse workforce through embedding diversity, equality and inclusion at all levels of our business, supporting people of various abilities and adopting a zero-tolerance approach for discrimination

Responsible business

We empower suppliers to create thriving businesses, rooted in responsible practices.

- Developing an ethical supply chain through safeguarding against corruption and protecting human rights across our operations
- Accountable and inclusive governance through compliance with legal and fiscal requirements, observance of our Code of Conduct and a designated Board of Directors to oversee our Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) strategy and progress

The Deoleo Sustainability Protocol

We aim to set the highest standards of sustainability for extra virgin olive oil production across all levels of the supply chain – from the olive tree to the table.

We believe more sustainable olive oil benefits everyone. It leads to higher quality for consumers, fair labour conditions for workers, greater care for the planet and economic security for suppliers.

The Deoleo Sustainability Protocol provides a frame of reference on sustainable management of olive oil mills throughout the supply chain. We believe in driving change in a collaborative way which is why each of the participating mills will work alongside a technician assigned by Deoleo who will offer specific guidance on how they can apply the Protocol requirements.

Those who wish to implement the Protocol can formalise their agreement to participate in the sustainable supply chain of extra virgin olive oil. This confirms their commitment to undertake the guidelines of the Protocol and help build a more sustainable future for our sector. Compliance will be assessed by a third party, allowing these mills to become accredited suppliers of sustainable extra virgin olive oil.

The Sustainability Protocol for extra virgin olive oil was launched in 2018 and has been improved and refined in 2022. Encompassing three key sustainability areas – Socio-economic, Environmental and Quality – we developed the Protocol in line with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Our shared objectives

Objective	Approach	Deoleo's actions	Protocol compliance	Contributing to the UN SDGs
<p>5 – Gender equality <i>Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls</i></p> <p>8 – Decent work and economic growth <i>Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all</i></p>				
<p>2 – Zero hunger <i>End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition, and promote sustainable agriculture</i></p> <p>3 – Good health and well-being <i>Ensure healthy lives and promote wellbeing for all at all ages</i></p>				
<p>12 – Responsible consumption and production <i>Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns</i></p> <p>13 – Climate action <i>Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts</i></p> <p>15 – Life on land <i>Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, halt and reverse land degradation, and halt biodiversity loss</i></p>				

Our approach

At Deoleo, we have a legacy of providing consumers with the best quality olive oil. It is in our best interests to protect this time-honoured product and push for the sustainable development of our sector.

The purpose of the Protocol

As leaders in the branding and distribution of extra virgin olive oil, it is our responsibility to ensure the future of this precious resource. That's why we form strong collaborations with our suppliers to support the passion and dedication of olive oil production and maintain it for years to come. The purpose of the Protocol is to support the different stages of our supply chain in the sustainable production of extra virgin olive oil. Beyond improving sustainability for society and environment, the Protocol is also designed to bring our suppliers business prosperity and operational resilience for the future.

Our vision at Deoleo is to continue increasing the number of certified partners we work with and improve the future of the olive oil sector.

How it works

To become a certified partner, suppliers must agree to contribute to a sustainable supply chain for extra virgin olive oil. This involves gradually incorporating the requirements outlined in the Protocol and undergoing regular assessment from third-party verifier, Intertek. Suppliers commit to following the Sustainability Protocol for a three-year period, during which they will be regularly assessed to ensure ongoing compliance with Protocol criteria. At the end of the three-year period, there is the option to renew the agreement.

By agreeing to participate, suppliers are agreeing to digital traceability throughout their supply chain. This visibility allows for greater transparency across both Deoleo and the wider sector. Following the Protocol supports increased protection and preservation of natural spaces, uplifts agricultural communities and safeguards human and labour rights.

We support suppliers to incorporate cutting-edge technology while preserving the legacy and heritage of olive oil cultivation to create a more sustainable sector.

Third-party verifiers identify mills who are integrating the Sustainability Protocol and provide certification that their olive oil comes from sustainable production. These suppliers can then display the logo, demonstrating to all who buy their olive oil that they are a verified product.

1.

Organisation and people

Supporting the passionate people who bring olive oil to tables worldwide

Why it matters

The olive oil sector provides valuable employment opportunities and economic stability, particularly in rural areas at risk of depopulation. By increasing access to resources and encouraging sustainable agricultural practices, we are helping our suppliers boost development in traditional farming communities, preparing them to become more climate-resilient and economically stable. In areas where the Protocol has been implemented, olive production represents between 50% and 90% of local employment¹.

Our shared objective

Generating sustainable economic growth by creating decent employment opportunities is a priority. Farming communities are increasingly impacted by risks such as market volatility,

climate change and ageing populations. By working together, we can support the safeguarding of rural livelihoods, economic development and futureproofing of these communities to preserve economic stability for generations to come.

Focus areas

Protecting worker livelihoods involves ensuring fair working conditions and inclusive growth opportunities for all people, including women, young people and other vulnerable groups. Working together, we can help identify opportunities for positive impact in communities, implement strategies to increase transparency, prevent workplace issues across the supply chain, comply with legal and fiscal obligations, and develop ways to measure progress.

¹ Source: page 16 – (Deoleo ESG Report 2021)

1. Organisation and people

Mandatory
 Basic level
 Intermediate level
 Advanced level

 Olive mill
 Olive grove

Requirement	Level
1.1. Compliance with obligations (permits, licenses and authorisations according to legislation in force) and responsible tax	
1.1.1 All the permits, deeds and records listed in the example evidence are owned.	
1.1.2 There is evidence that the organisation has registered its annual accounts, and is up to date with Social Security and Tax Agency payments.	
1.1.3 The annual accounts have been audited.	
1.2 Occupational safety and health	
1.2.1 The company has a plan for the prevention of occupational hazards for the provision of safe and healthy working conditions. The obligations and preventive measures established in the preventive plan are monitored. The required records are available for the audited sample.	
1.3 Good governance with respect to human rights	
1.3.1 The organisation has a policy that includes the following commitments: 1. consumer health protection, 2. protection and respect for the environment, including prevention of pollution, 3. provision of safe and healthy work environments, 4 respect for human rights and internationally accepted behaviour, 5. contribution to the development of the community, 6. continuous improvement, 7. compliance with the DEOLEO Sustainability Protocol. This policy is presented and communicated to the people who work in the organisation.	

Requirement	Level
1.4 Viability and business continuity	
1.4.1 The organisation has a calculation of general production costs and the manager of the organisation has professional training in its activity.	
1.4.2 The organisation has a calculation of general production costs (including cost per unit of production) and analysis of the trajectory of the organisation's economic results.	
1.4.3 The organisation has a medium or long-term strategic plan.	
1.4.4 The company has a documented organisational chart.	
1.4.5 The company has documented job profiles for each of the positions defined in the organisation chart.	
1.4.6 The company has a person responsible for sustainability management.	
1.4.7 The organisation makes specific investments and justification of the latest investments.	
1.4.8 The organisation has an investment plan for the innovation and technological update of the activity.	
1.4.9 The organisation has an analysis of the results of investments and returns on investment.	

1. Organisation and people

Mandatory

 Basic level

 Intermediate level

 Advanced level

Requirement	Level
1.5 Full employment, productive employment and decent work	
1.5.1 The right to collective bargaining and freedom of association has been communicated, regardless of whether the right has been exercised.	
1.5.2 If the right is exercised, it has been carried out transparently and independently.	
1.5.3 The company has provided technical training in the last year.	
1.5.4 The company has a training plan.	
1.5.5 The company has provided skills training (management of emotions, teamwork, stress management, motivation, leadership, etc.)	
1.5.6 The organisation has social benefits that are above what is established in its applicable collective labour agreement and are documented.	
1.5.7 The organisation has a work-life plan.	
1.6 Equal opportunities and combating discrimination	
1.6.1 The commitment to work toward equality between men and women has been communicated. There is foresight for the development of this commitment.	
1.6.2 The organisation has signed an agreement for equality between men and women.	
1.6.3 The organisation has hired women in the last 3 years.	
1.6.4 The organisation has carried out some type of action in favour of equality in the last 3 years.	
1.6.5 The organisation has an Equality Committee and an Equality plan.	

Requirement	Level
1.7 Social contribution to the community and promotion of employability	
1.7.1 The organisation sponsors and/or organises social activities periodically and they are documented.	
1.7.2 More than 50% of the workers are local.	
1.7.3 Some type of service has been carried out for the mill with local companies in the last three years.	
1.7.4 More than 50% of the companies that have carried out some type of service for the oil mill in the last three years are local.	
1.7.5 The organisation has hired people under 30 years of age in the last 3 years.	
1.7.6 The organisation has hired people over 45 years of age in the last 3 years.	
1.8 Information and data	
1.8.1 The organisation has a contract with a specialised company or documented evidence of carrying out computer equipment maintenance measures.	
1.8.2 Backup copies of the data are kept in custody outside the facilities. An updated antivirus is available. There is an active firewall.	
1.9 Voluntary Certifications	
1.9.1 ISO 9001 certification is in force.	
1.9.2 BRC/IFS/FSCC22000 certification is in force.	
1.9.3 ISO 14001 certification is in force.	
1.9.4 GLOBAL GAP or similar is in force.	

2.

Quality and food safety

Preserving olive oil at every step of its journey

Why it matters

With global problems of malnourishment and food-borne diseases increasingly prevalent, food safety and quality has never been more important. At Deoleo, we know that these issues need to be tackled at the source, and that the approach to the global system of food production needs to change.

Our shared objective

Focusing on adherence to internationally recognised food safety standards and more sustainable processes, we can work together to protect and preserve the environment and prevent risk of disease at all stages of production – maintaining food production and increasing access to safe food for years to come. Through this, we also ensure the great taste, safety and quality of the final product received by the consumer.

Focus areas

The final product depends on high-quality raw material and for that quality to be maintained from the initial olive to the production of the oil to the packaging and transporting of the bottles. That is why we ensure cleanliness, maintenance and traceability from field to table – to ensure only the highest standards of food safety and quality management.

2. Quality and food safety

- Mandatory
- Basic level
- Intermediate level
- Advanced level

Requirement	Level
2.1. Facilities	
2.1.1 During the visit it is shown that the facilities are within a closed perimeter that does not allow access by unauthorised persons.	● ○ ○ ○ ○
2.1.2 There are vehicle parking areas and they are defined, vehicles do not park in production and operational areas. A flow is defined for vehicles and people, with parking areas for visitors and transport or contractors. There is enough space for you to manoeuvre easily.	● ○ ○ ○ ○
2.1.3 There are verification mechanisms that control measures are appropriate (access control, closed access, parking areas) There is control of access to the production area.	● ● ○ ○ ○
2.1.4 Video surveillance is available	● ● ● ○ ○
2.2 Olive reception	
2.2.1 During the visit to the facilities, it is shown that it is not possible for vehicles to pass over the raw material reception hoppers.	● ○ ○ ○ ○
2.2.2 An evaluation/review of the olive is carried out at the reception.	● ○ ○ ○ ○
2.2.3 The weighing of the transports is carried out and the weight is not greater than 5,000 kg in more than 80% transport.	● ● ○ ○ ○
2.2.4 There are records of inspection of the quality of the olive. The record specifies the criteria that are checked (soil and flight, frost, fly, maturity stage, etc).	● ○ ○ ○ ○
2.2.5 There are records of inspection of the quality of the olive. The record specifies the criteria: variety.	● ● ○ ○ ○
2.2.6 There are records of inspection of the quality of the olive. The record specifies the criteria: damaged olive (frost, affected by pests) and/or state of maturation/quality (early olive, 1st tree, integrated certification etc).	● ● ○ ○ ○
2.2.7 It is evident that actions have been carried out in favour of the early harvest of the olive.	● ● ● ○ ○

Requirement	Level
2.3 Reception yard	
2.3.1 A plan to replace non-food grade belts with food grade belts is projected and documented and/or periodic controls are carried out to ensure the absence of phthalates in the product.	● ● ● ● ●
2.3.2 Food grade and phthalate free belts are used but not on all lines.	● ○ ○ ○ ○
2.3.3 Food grade and phthalate free belts are used on all lines.	● ● ○ ○ ○
2.3.4 The frequency of changing the water in the olive washer is adequate. The water has an acceptable appearance. There are records of the change of water in the washing machine.	● ○ ○ ○ ○
2.3.5 The olive is not stored in bags or they are made of food grade material.	● ● ● ● ●
2.3.6 The hoppers, where the olives are stored before starting to mill them, are covered.	● ● ○ ○ ○
2.3.7 The hoppers where the olives are stored before starting to grind them, are made of stainless steel or internally covered with epoxy paint, stainless steel.	● ● ○ ○ ○
2.3.8 The storage hoppers do not have angles where the olive can be retained, causing fermentation.	● ● ● ○ ○
2.3.9 There is a control system through production reports and records which verifies that the residence time of the olives in hoppers with a capacity of 40,000 kg is less than or equal to 24 hours (if fewer olives are stored, the time of permanence may be longer). If the mill stores the olives in boxes of a size equal to or less than 600 kg, the residence time is less than 24 hours.	● ○ ○ ○ ○

2. Quality and food safety

Mandatory
 Basic level
 Intermediate level
 Advanced level

 Olive mill
 Olive grove

Requirement	Level
2.3.10 There is a control system through production reports and records which verifies that the residence time of the olives in hoppers with a capacity of 40,000 kg is less than or equal to 12 hours (if fewer olives are stored, the time of permanence may be longer). If the mill stores the olives in boxes of a size equal to or less than 600 kg, the residence time is less than 24 hours.	● ● ○ ○
2.3.11 There is a control system through production reports and records which verifies that the residence time of the olives in hoppers with a capacity of 40,000 kg is less than or equal to 8 hours (if fewer olives are stored, the time of permanence may be longer). If the mill stores the olives in boxes of a size equal to or less than 600 kg, the residence time is less than 12 hours.	● ● ● ○
2.3.12 At the exit of the hoppers and/or at the entrance of the mills there are magnet elements for metal detection.	● ○ ○ ○
2.3.13 There is a record of operational control of the efficiency/cleanliness of the magnets.	● ● ○ ○
2.4 Plant	
2.4.1 It is ensured that the malaxation of olive paste time is less than or equal to 60 minutes with records to prove it.	● ● ○ ○
2.4.2 The malaxation of olive paste temperature is between 22°C and 25°C. There are records of temperature control (at least once a day).	● ● ○ ○
2.4.3 The malaxation of olive paste temperature is between 22°C and 25°C. There are computer records through integrated software.	● ● ● ○
2.4.4 The outlet temperature of the oil from the centrifuge is less than or equal to 27°C. There are temperature control records for each shift and/or each change in production conditions.	● ● ○ ○
2.4.5 Food grade greases and lubricants are used (Food grade H1 certificate).	● ● ● ●

Requirement	Level
2.4.6 It is not possible to contaminate the olive or the product with fats or lubricants.	● ● ○ ○
2.4.7 There is evidence of analysis of the MOSH and MOAHS content of the greases/lubricants used.	● ● ● ○
2.4.8 A certificate of suitability for use in the food industry is available for all cleaning products and adjuvants (eg talc, filtering earths, cellulose).	● ● ● ●
2.4.9 There are batch records of the use of technological aids (talc) used.	● ○ ○ ○
2.4.10 Food grade certificates and migration tests are available for pump stators.	● ● ● ●
2.5 Storage	
2.5.1 The decantation process is carried out and there are records that prove it.	● ● ○ ○
2.5.2 There are facilities to carry out the advanced filtration process (cellulose, with filtering soils...etc) of the oils obtained, this process is carried out and there are records that prove it.	● ● ● ○
2.5.3 Food-grade and phthalate-free hoses are used.	● ● ● ●
2.5.4 There is a temperature control system that ensures that the storage temperature of the oil is between 13-25 °C and there are temperature control records in the cellar.	● ● ○ ○
2.5.5 The storage tanks are made of stainless steel and are located in a closed space with little lighting.	● ○ ○ ○
2.5.6 Storage tanks have head space with inert gases.	● ● ● ○

2. Quality and food safety

- Mandatory
- Basic level
- Intermediate level
- Advanced level

Requirement	Level
2.6 Cleaning, Maintenance and Traceability	
2.6.1 Order and cleanliness are observed during the visit to the facilities. There are no bad smells. There is a cleaning plan and records of verification that correct cleaning activities have been carried out.	● ○ ○ ○ ○
2.6.2 There is a periodic maintenance plan and records of the maintenance tasks carried out.	● ○ ○ ○ ○
2.6.3 Field work machinery have maintenance records.	● ● ● ● ●
2.6.4 The field work machinery is registered in the Official Registry of Agricultural Machinery.	● ● ● ● ●
2.6.5 Product traceability is ensured during all stages of production and handling, as well as storage up to the point where the oil mill is no longer the owner of the product.	● ● ● ● ●
2.6.6 Oil drain operations are carried out, and there are records that prove it.	● ● ○ ○ ○
2.6.7 The traceability system is computerised. (Backup copies are made and specialised maintenance is available).	● ● ● ○ ○

Requirement	Level
2.7 HACCP	
2.7.1 There is an implemented HACCP study, which ensures that all the products they supply are safe from the point of view of food safety.	● ● ● ● ●
2.7.2 Chemical hazards other than pesticides have been identified (benzopyrenes, pthalates, etc).	● ○ ○ ○ ○
2.7.3 Good Handling and Manufacturing Practices are documented.	● ● ● ● ●
2.7.6 A pest control procedure is in place.	● ● ● ● ●

Water management and monitoring

Protecting a valuable, natural resource for future generations

Why it matters

Water is a critical resource for people and planet alike. It's also critical in agriculture – from small holds to industrial operations. Water-scarcity is a real and significant threat, with more than 733 billion people estimated to live in countries with high and critical levels of water stress.

As a company with huge global reach, it is our responsibility to ensure efficient use of water across our supply chain.

Another key concern is keeping water resources free from pollution. With water pollution an ever-increasing problem, we need to act now to mitigate risk of pollution across the supply chain. Water pollution can occur as a direct consequence of industrial wastewater discharges, the use of agrochemicals, inadequate disposal of waste and extreme weather phenomena caused by climate change.

Our shared objective

Maximising the efficiency of water consumption across our collective processes can reduce waste, save money and make these operations sustainable, contributing to the longevity of this natural resource to cover demands in the future.

Focus areas

We work together to make water usage more efficient, reduce wastewater and improve water quality. At Deoleo, we are not merely concerned with addressing the here and now but also with creating more sustainable water management practices for the future.

3. Water management and monitoring

Mandatory
 Basic level
 Intermediate level
 Advanced level

 Olive mill
 Olive grove

Requirement	Level
3.1 Water supply	
3.1.1 In accordance with the applicable legislation, there is evidence of permits for the collection and/or use of water from all sources and/or water consumption.	● ● ● ●
3.2 Water quality	
3.2.1 Annual analysis of the organoleptic and microbiological quality of the water used in the process is carried out.	● ● ● ●
3.2.2 Chlorine and organoleptic analyses are carried out in accordance with the applicable legislation.	● ● ● ●
3.2.3 Annual analysis is carried out by an external laboratory, of the organoleptic and microbiological quality of the water used in the process.	● ● ○ ○
3.2.4 An analysis of water for irrigation has been carried out in the last 3 years.	● ● ○ ○
3.3 Management and efficient use of water	
3.3.1 Water consumption is recorded systematically and is individualised for oil production.	● ○ ○ ○
3.3.2 Existence of documented good management practices and efficient use of water.	● ○ ○ ○
3.3.3 An inventory of water uses is available.	● ○ ○ ○
3.3.4 Water consumption is measured in relation to the production unit.	● ● ○ ○

Requirement	Level
3.3.5 Water consumption is taken at least every 15 days.	● ● ○ ○
3.3.6 Objectives are established to reduce water consumption.	● ● ● ○
3.3.7 The water consumption of each section of the process is quantified.	● ● ● ○
3.3.8 There are control records of the conditions of the transport and water supply facilities.	● ○ ○ ○
3.3.9 There are records of the use of the water collected.	● ● ○ ○
3.3.10 It is periodically checked that the farm is irrigated in a uniform manner.	● ● ○ ○
3.3.11 A visual inspection of the state of the irrigation and water facilities (pipes, couplings and intakes) is carried out.	● ● ○ ○
3.3.12 Preventive maintenance of the irrigation installation is carried out and there is a record of the tasks realised.	● ● ● ○
3.3.13 Drip irrigation is used.	● ● ○ ○
3.3.14 Subterranean drip irrigation is used.	● ● ● ○
3.3.14 There is a justified and documented knowledge of the calculation of the dose and frequency of irrigation based on scientific knowledge of the crop development cycle and its sensitivity to water stress in each phase, also to the need for crop water by direct or indirect methods, or by making use of the public system of advice to the irrigator.	● ○ ○ ○

3. Water management and monitoring

Mandatory

 Basic level

 Intermediate level

 Advanced level

 Olive mill
 Olive grove

Requirement	Level
3.3.15 There is an irrigation notebook that documents the irrigation planning and execution process.	● ● ○ ○
3.3.17 It has a water footprint verified by an independent entity.	● ● ● ○
3.3.18 There are documented and demonstrable reduction plans for the reduction of the water footprint.	● ● ● ○
3.3.19 The organisation has an automated irrigation system to optimise the use of water.	● ● ○ ○
3.3.20 The organisation has an automated irrigation system that calculates the dose and frequency of irrigation according to the information received from climate-soil-olive tree sensors.	● ● ● ○
3.3.21 It is evident that the limits of water use of 1,500 m³/ha for intensive and 2,500 m³/ha for super-intensive are met.	● ● ○ ○
3.3.22 The organisation reuses rainwater.	● ● ● ○

Energy efficiency management

Reducing the carbon footprint of every process

Why it matters

If significant changes are not made to the way we manufacture food, the production of extra virgin olive oil will continue to depend on non-renewable fossil fuels. With global oil and natural gas reserves expected to be exhausted within the next 35 to 40 years, it is crucial for us to change these processes to become more energy efficient. That's why we are focused on increased use of renewable energies in the production of extra virgin olive oil.

Measuring and reducing energy consumption within our own operations, as well as the operations of our partners, will help us to lower our footprint – something which is not only positively impactful for the planet, but which translates as financial savings for us and our suppliers.

Our shared objective

Collaboration is key to working towards a low-carbon future with zero waste. We can continue to be more energy efficient across our collective processes. Joining together to target a steady, long-term emission reduction and transition to more renewable energy sources, we have the power to create change and preserve the future of our sector.

Focus areas

We have the potential to create positive impact for our planet and society, through transforming production models for more efficient management and use of energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and investing in low-carbon technologies for manufacturing.

4. Energy efficiency management

Mandatory
 Basic level
 Intermediate level
 Advanced level

 Olive mill
 Olive grove

Requirement	Level
4.1 Energy supply	
4.1.1 In accordance with the applicable legislation, evidence of permission is provided for the capture and/or use of energy from all sources and/or energy consumption. Energy contracts exist in the company's name.	● ● ● ●
4.2 Management and efficient use of energy	
4.2.1 There are reliable energy consumption records (energy meters and/or energy bills) individualised for oil production.	● ○ ○ ○ ○
4.2.2 Energy consumption is recorded systematically.	● ● ○ ○ ○
4.2.3 Existence of good management practices and efficient use of energy documented.	● ● ○ ○ ○
4.2.4 Goals are set to reduce energy consumption.	● ● ● ○ ○
4.2.5 There is an energy efficiency audit report.	● ● ● ○ ○
4.3 Reduction of greenhouse gas emission	
4.3.1 The organisation has a biomass boiler.	● ○ ○ ○ ○
4.3.2 The organisation has 100% biomass boilers.	● ● ○ ○ ○
4.3.2 The organisation has the installation of solar panels in the mill.	● ● ● ○ ○
4.3.3 Electric or hybrid company vehicles and/or charging points for electric vehicles.	● ● ● ○ ○
4.3.4 There is a verified carbon footprint calculation.	● ● ● ○ ○

Requirement	Level
4.3.5 There are documented and demonstrable reduction plans for the reduction of the carbon footprint.	● ● ● ○ ○
4.3.6 Reduce the use of non-renewable energy sources and increase the use of renewable energy sources.	● ● ● ○ ○
4.3.7 Optimisation of the use of inputs with high energy consumption such as inorganic fertilisers.	● ○ ○ ○ ○
4.3.8 Optimising the use of appropriate agricultural machinery.	● ○ ○ ○ ○
4.3.10 Prevent loss of plant cover or introduce plant cover.	● ● ○ ○ ○
4.3.11 Spread the manure and leave it on the surface and prohibit the injection of liquid manure into the soil or its direct introduction into the soil.	● ● ● ○ ○
4.3.12 Use advanced formulation fertilisers, such as slow-release and low-carbon fertilisers, or fertiliser additives such as urease inhibitors or nitrification.	● ● ● ○ ○
4.3.13 Build soil carbon with cover crops.	● ● ● ○ ○
4.3.14 Building soil carbon with conservation tillage.	● ● ○ ○ ○
4.3.15 There is a biofuel supply point in the cooperative.	● ● ● ○ ○
4.4 Air pollution sources	
4.4.1 There is evidence of the registration of existing atmospheric sources and mandatory periodic regulatory inspections.	● ● ● ● ●

 5.

Soil management and conservation

Valuing the natural power of healthy soil

Why it matters

With soil being the foundation of all agricultural production, one of the biggest threats to agricultural activity is soil erosion. It's an issue that has the potential to prevent adequate food production to serve a global population. Annually, 12 million hectares of land² are no longer cultivable and 50% of agricultural land worldwide is already degraded.

When soils are allowed to degrade, precious nutrients are lost and our planet is at risk of biodiversity loss, ecosystem instability, lack of nature conservation and reduction of food production across the world. Olive cultivation practices specifically can involve the elimination of vegetation cover, intensive ploughing, use of pesticides and chemical fertilisers – all of which impact soil's capacity to sequester carbon.

Our shared objective

A sustainable future for the olive oil sector relies on correct soil management and maintenance. No one knows about their specific soil more than the farmers themselves. Working hand in hand, farmers and Deoleo technicians can create a bespoke soil maintenance system for each farm – bringing together farm-specific expertise with a legacy of industry knowledge and sustainability practices. These soil maintenance systems are designed with both the present and future in mind – created to support the optimisation of water use, reduction of nutrient loss and maximisation of the soil's carbon sink properties while reducing risks for the future and promoting long-term fertility.

Focus areas

When we work together, we are focused on implementing ways to measure ground productivity and biological activity to maximise yield and minimise contribution to soil erosion and degradation.

² Source: [United Nations Press Release].

5. Soil management and conservation

Requirement	Level	Requirement	Level
5.1 Soil operational control		5.2.10 Management of stocking rates through rotation in animal grazing, to prevent loss of plant cover and soil compaction.	
5.1.1 There is complete and traceable sampling of the soil condition every five years, and/or according to specialist recommendations.	● ● ● ○ ○		
5.1.2 Prior to the start of exploitation (new plantations), the organisation has carried out a study of the suitability of the soil.	● ● ● ○ ○	5.3 Measures to increase biological activity and soil productivity	
5.2 Measures to prevent soil erosion and compaction		5.3.1 Minimisation of soil tillage to preserve the structure.	● ○ ○ ○ ○
5.2.1 Use of minimum impact machinery (disc plow, disc harrow, chisel plow, subsoiler, among others).	● ○ ○ ○ ○		
5.2.2 Maintenance or improvement of the plant cover of the soils, avoiding that soils remain uncovered.	● ○ ○ ○ ○		
5.2.3 Minimum or zero tillage (comply with the rules of integrated production of the olive grove).	● ○ ○ ○ ○		
5.2.4 Mulch-type coverage or incorporation of pruning remains in the planting row.	● ○ ○ ○ ○		
5.2.5 Soil levelling to prevent runoff.	● ○ ○ ○ ○		
5.2.6 Use of plants that promote soil enrichment in nutrients (such as nitrogen).	● ● ● ○ ○		
5.2.7 Gully control (use of the plow or harrow at the beginning of the gully, and/or through the protection of the upper part of the gully by installing bags, seeding or redirecting the water flows to ditches on the sides of the gullies).	● ● ● ○ ○		
5.2.8 Localised irrigation.	● ● ● ○ ○		
5.2.9 Use of organic amendments to improve the structure and water retention capacity of the soil.	● ● ● ○ ○		

Biodiversity management

Working in harmony with the natural world

Why it matters

A more sustainable future relies on biodiversity protection – supporting all life on earth to flourish. Increasing awareness about biodiversity preservation is crucial for reducing species loss and encouraging more sustainable alternatives to become common practice. Understanding the direct and indirect causes of biodiversity loss can help suppliers combat these effects and minimise risks.

Our shared objective

Olive oil production poses significant risk to biological diversity, yet it also suffers greatly from the effects. This is why it is crucial to join together to assess our collective production processes and business strategy to minimise our impact on landscape and nature conservation. Working together, we can adopt new measures designed to protect endangered animal and plant species and make our processes more sustainable in the long term.

Focus areas

The Protocol focuses on the conservation of biodiversity. From ants, insects, birds, small mammals and reptiles to invaluable flora and fauna, we want to emphasise their importance and introduce ways to promote conservation across production processes.

6. Biodiversity management

Mandatory
 Basic level
 Intermediate level
 Advanced level

 Olive mill
 Olive grove

Requirement	Level
6.1 Biodiversity conservation planning	
6.1.1 There is evidence of the existence of a biodiversity plan.	● ● ● ●
6.1.2 The existence of a type of olive grove with a life expectancy of more than 30 years is evidenced, which implies a fixation of biodiversity in the long term.	● ○ ○ ○
6.1.3 There is evidence of the implementation of the actions included in the biodiversity plan and its periodic review.	● ○ ○ ○
6.1.4 There is evidence of the implementation of the actions included in the biodiversity plan with a degree of compliance of at least 50% and its periodic review.	● ● ○ ○
6.1.5 There is evidence of the implementation of the actions included in the biodiversity plan with a degree of compliance of at least 90% and its periodic review.	● ● ● ○
6.1.6 There are alliances with other organisations to improve biodiversity.	● ● ● ○
6.1.7 Maintenance and conservation of native varieties of olive trees.	● ● ● ○
6.2 Conservation actions for birds	
6.2.1 Night harvesting is not carried out.	● ● ● ●
6.2.2 Decreased use of insecticides applied to trees to increase food availability for insectivorous birds associated with the trunk of olive trees.	● ○ ○ ○
6.2.3 Construction of infrastructures such as nests, birds perches, ponds, etc.	● ● ○ ○
6.2.4 Installation and/or maintenance of isolated trees of high size, producers of fruits, pinecones or acorns that attract insectivorous and frugivorous birds of all kinds and that serve as innkeepers and observation points.	● ● ○ ○

Requirement	Level
6.2.5 Maintenance and installation of small water points (fountains) and pools frequented by birds and many other vertebrates during the summer and which are also a source of insects.	● ● ○ ○
6.2.6 Presence of stone walls used by birds that breed in holes in the ground.	● ● ○ ○
6.2.7 Installation of artificial nesting boxes in human constructions since the lack of nesting sites in other places or farms can limit the appearance or abundance of some species.	● ● ● ○
6.2.8 Restoration and repopulation work is carried out on roads, boundaries, gullies, slopes or streams with native species.	● ● ● ○
6.2.9 In the event of massive replacement of old olive trees with new olive groves, avoid or reduce the removal and replacement of old olive trees with new ones, which affects insectivorous trunk birds and other vertebrates that use the replaced trunks.	● ● ● ○
6.3 Actions for the proliferation of pollinators	
6.3.1 Reduction or elimination of the massive and indiscriminate use of pesticides.	● ○ ○ ○
6.3.2 Restoration of plant covers rich in functional groups with flowers attractive to insects.	● ○ ○ ○
6.3.3 Creation of nesting places for solitary bees through artificial nests ('bee hotels').	● ● ● ○
6.3.4 Installation of hives for the honey bee in the environment of the olive groves.	● ● ● ○
6.4 Actions for the proliferation of ants and other insects	
6.4.1 Maintenance of the presence and/or recovery of remnants of natural habitat, plant covers and other unproductive vegetated areas in the olive grove landscape.	● ○ ○ ○
6.4.2 Planting or maintenance of boundaries with plant species that function as a refuge for native fauna and as an attraction for predatory insects of olive tree pests.	● ● ○ ○

6. Biodiversity management

Requirement	Level
6.5 Actions for the conservation of weed/undergrowth plants	
6.5.1 Avoid the use of herbicides.	● ○ ○ ○ ○
6.5.2 Encourage change from intensive plant covers management (pre-emergence herbicides or ploughing) to extensive plant covers management (plant cover maintenance and mowing, preferably mechanical).	● ● ○ ○ ○
6.5.3 Maintenance and enrichment of plant covers.	● ○ ○ ○ ○
6.5.4 Develop specific actions to diversify the olive grove landscape, by restoring natural elements in unproductive areas (green infrastructure).	● ● ● ○ ○
6.6 Actions for the conservation of small mammals and reptiles	
6.6.1 Planting or maintenance of boundaries with plant species that function as a refuge for native fauna and as an attraction for predatory insects of olive tree pests.	● ● ○ ○ ○
6.6.2 Maintenance and installation of small water points (fountains) and pools easily used by different species of mammals, amphibians and invertebrates.	● ● ● ○ ○
6.6.3 Existence of stone walls used as shelter by numerous fauna.	● ● ● ○ ○

Waste and by-product management

Aiming for a less wasteful, circular economy

Why it matters

We understand that current systems must change in order to protect and preserve natural resources for the future. More sustainable production of extra virgin olive oil relies on maximising resource efficiency and minimising the generation of waste – creating a circular economy which positively contributes to more profitable, sustainable and environmentally friendly production.

Our shared objective

Together, we can approach waste and by-production in a more responsible and more innovative way, rethinking how we could repurpose limited resources' waste products such as water. Replenishing the planet during our processes leaves a positive footprint behind, working towards a more sustainable, less wasteful future.

Focus areas

We are focused on efficient management of residual waste, repurposing the residual water generated through olive oil production and innovating new ways to use by-products, all to promote a circular economy and positively contribute to the sustainability of the sector.

7. Waste and by-product management

Mandatory
 Basic level
 Intermediate level
 Advanced level

 Olive mill
 Olive grove

Requirement	Level
7.1 Waste management	
7.1.1 Authorisation for the production of hazardous and non-hazardous waste is available in accordance with applicable legislation.	● ● ● ●
7.1.2 There is a contract with an authorised manager for the waste produced. Two deliveries of waste are verified and proof of delivery or control and monitoring is available.	● ● ● ●
7.1.3 There is a physical or computerised record book for all hazardous waste. Two deliveries of waste are verified and correctly registered.	● ● ● ●
7.1.4 There is a physical or computerised record book for all non-hazardous waste. Two deliveries of waste are verified and registered correctly.	● ● ○ ○
7.1.5 It is verified that the SIGFITO POINT or equivalent is roofed and has a waterproof screed.	● ○ ○ ○
7.1.6 It is verified that at the SIGFITO POINT or equivalent, the containers are inside the bags and these are correctly labelled.	● ○ ○ ○
7.1.7 It is evident during the visit that the storage of hazardous waste has good waste segregation, container labelling, order and cleanliness.	● ○ ○ ○
7.1.8 It is evident during the visit that the storage of non-hazardous waste has good waste segregation, container labelling, order and cleanliness.	● ● ○ ○
7.1.9 It is evident that the staff responsible for waste management is trained.	● ● ○ ○
7.1.10 There is a waste management guide.	● ● ○ ○
7.2 By-products management and circular economy	
7.2.1 The reuse of the olive pit for the boiler is evidenced.	● ○ ○ ○
7.2.2 It is evident that the bone is certified.	● ● ● ○

Requirement	Level
7.2.3 The organisation provides firewood collection and management services to the members of the cooperatives.	● ● ● ○
7.2.4 The alperujo is removed by a company specialised in its recovery.	● ● ○ ○
7.2.5 The organisation has a composting plant.	● ● ● ○
7.2.6 The leaves are removed for recovery.	● ● ● ○
7.2.9 There is a record of all the by-products produced, quantities and final use.	● ● ○ ○
7.3 Process residual water management	
7.3.1 The organisation correctly manages the wastewater it generates in accordance with current and applicable legislation.	● ● ● ●
7.3.2 The transport of residual water to the pond is carried out by collectors.	● ● ○ ○
7.3.3 The transport of residual water to the pond is carried out by gravity.	● ● ● ○
7.3.4 The organisation carries out a pre-treatment of the residual water before it is discharged or deposited in a pond.	● ● ○ ○
7.3.6 According to the forecast of the campaign, the storage capacity in a wastewater pond is dimensioned.	● ● ○ ○
7.3.8 The organisation reuses treated wastewater. There are quality records of the wastewater reused before its use.	● ● ● ○
7.3.9 There are indicators of the consumption of treated residual water with respect to the total water used.	● ● ● ○

Agrochemical management

Caring for olive groves in a responsible way

Why it matters

Producing enough food for a growing population has led to increased use of agrochemicals in today's agricultural practices. However, this constant production is not sustainable. According to the United Nations, the world's population is expected to reach 9.6 billion by 2050 – a figure which would require the natural resources of almost three planets if we wish to maintain current lifestyles.

Our shared objective

Joining forces, Deoleo technicians, mill technicians and farmers can reevaluate current agrochemical practices across the supply chain to ensure that olive grove fertilisation is done in a way that is both productive and sustainable. Combining existing practices with sustainability guidelines, we can collaborate to create a bespoke approach to agrochemical

management, taking into account the conditions and functioning of soils and the nutritional needs of crops. From this, we can determine what is strictly necessary for soil productivity, minimising unnecessary use of fertilisers and agrochemicals.

Focus areas

Sustainable agrochemical application and storage management across the supply chain ensures that we are doing our part to protect people and the environment through more responsible agrochemical use.

8. Agrochemical management

Requirement	Level
8.1 Management and efficient use of agrochemicals	
8.1.1 There is a system by which the advisor or field technician always consults the official list of authorised agrochemical products on the web.	● ● ● ●
8.1.2 Leaf analyses are carried out periodically and traceable.	● ○ ○ ○
8.1.2 The organisation systematically informs partners about pests that are affecting crops locally and the recommended solutions.	● ○ ○ ○
8.1.3 The organisation has its own field technicians to advise the farms to the partners.	● ● ○ ○
8.1.4 The people in charge of the use of agrochemicals are trained in their responsible use.	● ● ● ●
8.1.5 The application of agrochemical products takes into account the minimisation and optimisation of the use of agrochemicals through treatment orders.	● ○ ○ ○
8.1.6 The application of agrochemical products takes into account the weather forecast (temperature, humidity, rain or wind).	● ● ○ ○
8.1.7 The application of agrochemical products takes into account the state of the soil where the agrochemical is applied (do not apply on frozen, compacted, cracked soil, with stagnant water or on slopes).	● ● ● ○
8.1.8 They only use agrochemicals approved by the Integrated Olive Production Standard.	● ● ○ ○
8.1.9 They only use agrochemicals approved by the Organic Production Standard.	● ● ● ○
8.1.9 There is a favourable report without deviation from the inspection of compliance with the integrated production regulations.	● ● ○ ○

Requirement	Level
8.1.10 There is a favourable report without deviation from the inspection of compliance with the Organic production regulations.	● ● ● ○
8.1.11 The organisation has implemented some technology related to precision agriculture.	● ● ● ○
8.1.12 Efficient sprayer utilisation.	● ● ○ ○
8.2 Agrochemical warehouse management	
8.2.1 The agrochemical product warehouse is registered in the Official Registry of Producers and Operators of Phytosanitary Defence.	● ● ● ●
8.2.2 The storage of agrochemical products is carried out in cabinets, in rooms or in premises intended solely for that purpose on waterproofed ground.	● ● ● ●
8.2.3 The storage is correctly marked and there are means of retaining leaks of up to 10% of the stored load.	● ● ● ●
8.2.4 The layout of the storage ensures that it is away from bodies of surface water or water extraction wells and from places or areas that can be flooded in the event of floods and separated from any inhabited premises.	● ● ● ●
8.2.5 There is an emergency plan and response capacity for leaks or spills of agrochemicals during storage.	● ● ● ●
8.2.6 The personnel who store the agrochemicals have training on safe handling, good practices and incompatibilities in the storage of agrochemicals.	● ● ● ●
8.2.7 The organisation has records of quantities (kg) of agrochemicals sold systematically and divided by type of agrochemical.	● ● ● ○

Definitions

Extra virgin olive oil

Superior category olive oil, obtained directly from olives and only by mechanical processes, whose characteristics comply with point 1 of Annex I of Regulation (EEC) No. 2568/91 of the Commission of 11 July 1991 on the characteristics of olive oils and olive-pomace oils and on their methods of analysis (and subsequent modifications).

Environment

In accordance with ISO 14001: 2015, the environment is the environment in which the organisation operates to carry out its activity and where its facilities can be found. This includes water, air, soil, natural resources, flora and fauna, human beings and all their interactions. The environment can range from the inside of an organisation to the local, regional and global system. The environment can be described in terms of biodiversity, ecosystems, climate and other characteristics.

Environmental impact

In accordance with ISO 14001: 2015, environmental impact is any change in the environment, whether beneficial or adverse, that occurs as a total or partial result of the environmental aspects of an organisation.

Biodiversity

According to the definition given in the 1992 Convention on Biological Diversity, biodiversity is the variability of living organisms from any source, including, among others, terrestrial and marine ecosystems and other aquatic systems, and the ecological complexes of which they are part; understands diversity within each species, between species and ecosystems. In biodiversity, three levels are often differentiated, closely related to each other, genetic diversity, diversity of species and diversity of spaces or ecosystems.

Olive oil production

For this Protocol, olive oil production is understood to mean all the phases necessary to obtain olive oil, from the field to the packaging thereof.

Food safety

Management system implemented and based on continuous improvement to achieve food safety.

Traceability

According to the Codex Alimentarius, "Traceability is the ability to follow the movement of a food through specified stage(s) of production, transformation and distribution."

Discrimination

For this Protocol, we understand discrimination as related to gender, race, ideology, religion, culture, nationality, marital status, age, sexual orientation or any other aspect.

References

Guide for the production of quality oils

Deoleo Sustainability Protocol checklist requirements

Publications consulted

- ISO 17000:2004 Conformity assessment – Vocabulary and general principles
- ISO 17011:2004 Conformity assessment – General requirements for accreditation bodies accrediting conformity assessment bodies
- ISO 17021:2011 Conformity assessment – Requirements for bodies providing audit and certification of management systems
- ISO FDIS 17065 Conformity assessment – Requirements for bodies certifying products, processes and services
- ISO DIS 17067 Conformity assessment – Fundamentals of product certification
- ISO 26000:2010 Guidance on Social Responsibility
- ISO 31010:2009 Risk management – Risk assessment techniques MSC Chain of Custody Methodology, v7 (2010)
- Regulation CE 852/2014 and its subsequent amendments regarding the hygiene of food products
- Regulation EC 1881/2006 and its subsequent modifications by which the maximum content of certain contaminants of food products is fixed
- Regulation 29/2012 and its subsequent amendments on the marketing rules for olive oil
- Law 42/2007 on the natural heritage and biodiversity

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